

The scyphozoan jellyfish, *Thysanostoma* spp. and their ectosymbiotic interactions in the Philippines

Citation:

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Summary

This study records the symbiotic interactions between scyphomedusae (*Thysanostoma* spp.) and various fish species in the coastal waters of the Philippines. Three species of *Thysanostoma* were identified using historical jellyfish descriptions. Observations revealed associations between *Thysanostoma* medusae and fish species such as *Carangoides ferdau*, *Carangoides dinema*, and *Aluterus* sp. Notably, a unique oral grasping behaviour was documented, where fish attach to the medusae without consuming them. These findings contribute to the understanding of marine symbiotic relationships and the ecological roles of *Thysanostoma* spp. in their natural habitats.

Figure S2. Scyphomedusae (*Thysanostoma* spp.) and their symbiotic interactions in the Philippines. **(a)** Medusae of the three species of *Thysanostoma* (coloured circles) occur in many coastal waters in the Philippines including Mabini, Batangas and they were identified using jellyfish descriptions in Jarms and Morandini (2019; 2023); Haeckel (1879); Mayer (1910); Stiasny (1923 and 1940); Schultze (1898); Tokioka and Nishimura (1970) and Zakai and Galil (2001). The medusae of Philippine *Thysanostoma* spp, associated with *Carangoides ferdau*, *Carangoides dinema*, *Aluterus* sp. (with *T. thysanura*) **(b-d; in situ**, R. Yoro), and another *C. ferdau* with *T. flagellatum* **(e; Wayne Jones pers. comm. with images)**. Remarkably, the fish in *d* exhibits oral grasping behaviour in which the fish “attaches itself on an object” by biting (but not consuming) the medusa (jellyfish bell remained intact in the observations in this study, *sensu* Eyal et al. 2011). Scale bars: b. 4 cm, c. 2 cm, d. 1 cm, e. 4 cm.

Fig. S2 Continuation

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